

Multiple Freeze-Thaw Cycles in Aquatic Foods: Review of Product Quality

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Abstract

Aquatic foods are among the most beneficial nutritional products, boasting numerous beneficial components for human health. Freezing is widely used for long-term preservation of processed aquatic foods. However, improper freezing and particularly post-freezing temperature fluctuations affect product quality. Especially the large size of slowly freezing ice crystals, the movement of water between the tissues as a result of thawing and refreezing, and the recrystallization reduce the physical, chemical, and microbiological quality values. As a result, product texture is damaged, protein denaturation results in decreased water holding capacity (WHC), and various adverse effects, such as color loss and increased lipid oxidation, occur. Numerous studies have investigated the application of multiple Freeze-Thaw (F-T) cycles to aquatic foods to determine these effects. These studies have focused on determining the changes that occur because of multiple F-T cycles, as well as methods to reduce their effects. Optimizing freezing and thawing processes, adding different additives, glazing, and using novel technologies such as ultrasound are among the methods being investigated to reduce the negative effects of multiple F-T cycles in aquatic foods. In this review, studies on multiple F-T cycles in aquatic foods are compiled and their effects and prevention methods are presented with the literature.

Keywords: *Multiple freeze-thaw cycles, Aquatic food, Temperature fluctuation*

Introduction

Aquatic foods are of great importance in the world market due to their valuable components and increasing consumption every year ¹. As is the case with all foods, consumers' interests in food safety and quality are the most important factors in purchasing aquatic products ². Aquatic food is sensitive to microbial and enzymatic activity and is among perishable food products ³. Temperature control is critical to ensuring proper food quality during food storage and transportation ⁴. Freezing is one of the most effective preservation methods used to extend the shelf life of foods and maintain their reliability ⁵. With this process, spoilage processes such as microbial growth and enzymatic reactions slow down, and the shelf life of the product is extended. However, rather than offering a solution, the freezing process also brings with it some challenges.

The freezing process causes changes in muscle tissue through the formation and deposition of ice crystals, dehydration, and increased solute concentration ⁶. Developments in freezing technology are effective in reducing undesirable changes that occur in the product during storage ³. For example, creating a layer of ice on the surface of the products by spraying or immersion in water (glazing) is an important preservation method for frozen fish ⁷.

During the storage, transportation, and sale of frozen products, water within the product may undergo thawing and refreezing due to disruptions in the cold

chain or temperature fluctuations. Ice crystals recrystallize due to fluctuations in storage temperature, which, depending on their size, can damage muscle and protein properties ⁸. In multiple freeze-thaw (F-T) cycles, ice crystals can cause mechanical damage to cell membranes and organelles ⁹. Therefore, multiple F-T cycles can cause significant reductions in the quality of aquatic products. The growth, melting and recrystallization of ice crystals formed as a result of F-T cycles, especially in processes such as production, transportation and storage, damages the structure of muscle tissue and leads to the breakage of chemical bonds in proteins ¹⁰. The continuity of the freeze-thaw process also causes more damage to the product ¹¹. Therefore, F-T cycles cause undesirable changes such as deterioration in cell structure, decrease in protein content, lipid oxidation, color changes, water loss, which reduces the likability of the product ¹².

In order to prevent the negative effects that may occur as a result of F-T cycles, the addition of cryoprotectants, various additives^{5,10,13,14}, seafood hydrolysates ¹⁵, ICP protein ¹⁶ and some advanced technological processes can also be used ^{3,17}. It is important to understand the mechanism of multiple F-T cycles to preserve the quality of aquatic food⁴. Excessive freeze-thaw cycles create problems in terms of food safety and economic losses. The aim of this study is to examine the quality losses that may occur after multiple F-T cycles in aquatic foods, the mechanisms that cause these losses, and the methods used to reduce these negative effects, according to

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the literature.

Basic Principles of Freezing and Thawing

Freezing is an effective method to preserve the quality of aquatic food and is based on the principle that the usable water decreases because of the formation of ice crystals¹⁸. However, since traditional freezing methods do not reach very low temperatures, all freezable water cannot be frozen and the product may spoil, albeit slowly¹⁹. In addition, ice crystals formed during freezing can negatively affect product quality by causing mechanical damage to the texture of the product¹⁶. The formation of ice crystals occurs in three stages: nucleation, ice crystal growth, and recrystallization (Figure 1)²⁰. When the temperature reaches the freezing point, water molecules gather in the same molecular configuration as ice crystals, then crystallization begins and water molecules are added to the crystals, and the temperature drops rapidly to storage temperature⁵. Recrystallization can occur through the accumulation, merging, transport or diffusion of water in a region due to temperature fluctuations²⁰.

Figure 1. The formation of ice crystals

Recrystallization, which occurs with temperature fluctuations in the frozen product, reduces the number of ice crystals and increases their volume²¹. The large crystals damage the cell membrane and muscle structure, leading to quality losses¹³. In the research conducted using nuclear magnetic resonance technique, it was reported that there is a relationship between the mobility of water during freezing and thawing and this damage in the forms of water that are tightly bound to macromolecules in the food matrix and free in the cell membrane and between cells²². Therefore, the free water content decreases with the freezing process, water migration occurs from intramyofibrillar spaces to intermyofibrillar spaces with F-T cycles, and the size of ice crystals changes during frozen storage²⁰.

The frozen product is then thawed with air, water, vacuum, contact thawing, etc. for use²³. However, thawing and refreezing may occur in the frozen product due to temperature fluctuations, which leads to negative effects on product quality¹⁹.

Effects of Multiple Freeze-Thaw Cycles on Quality

Although freezing is an effective method used to preserve the quality of aquatic food, problems arising from temperature fluctuations cause problems in terms of processing and consumption²⁴. Muscle tissue and cells undergo some irreversible changes and are damaged by

freeze-thaw cycles resulting from temperature fluctuations³. The findings of some studies conducted using F-T cycles in aquatic foods are presented in Table 1.

Quality changes in aquatic foods resulting from multiple F-T cycles can be classified as physical, chemical and microbiological quality.

Physical Quality

One of the most important physical changes is the growth of small ice crystals and recrystallization because of temperature fluctuations. As a result, irreversible structural damage occurs in the muscle tissue²³. Although water is one of the most important components of aquatic food, the growth of ice crystals during freezing significantly affects the physical quality of the product¹⁵. The freezing process, especially when repeated, causes denaturation of protein and damage to muscle fibers⁶. Lan et al., 2020⁽²⁸⁾ reported that protein denaturation and endomysium degradation occur with F-T cycles, and this is due to the repeated formation of ice crystals. It has also been reported that the pores between myofibrils increase, and the myofibril array differentiates with multiple F-T cycles³².

It is reported that protein denaturation resulting from multiple F-T cycles also affects WHC²⁸. In the LF-NMR method used to examine the distribution and mobility of water, it was stated that the mobility of bound water increased as a result of mechanical damage, and this is considered as evidence of a decrease in WHC⁸. The decrease in WHC value with multiple F-T cycles has been reported in many studies^{17,14}. Drip loss, one of the indicators of WHC, also increases because of protein denaturation with multiple F-T cycles²⁹.

Chemical Quality

Chemical quality changes occur because of irreversible reactions in aquatic products, especially in proteins and lipids, as a result of multiple F-T cycles³³. In aquatic foods, the structure of proteins is disrupted due to the formation of large ice crystals, which accelerates denaturation²⁹. The decrease in sulfhydryl groups and the increase in carbonyl content in proteins are chemical indicators of oxidation³⁴. This oxidation causes structural damage and loss of various properties in proteins³⁵. WHC reduction, cooking losses, textural defects are examples of these properties³².

In addition to proteins, many chemical changes are observed in lipid content with multiple F-T cycles, especially the oxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids³⁶. Although biochemical reactions slow down in frozen foods due to low water activity, lipid oxidation can occur even below 0.1 a_w³⁶. Temperature fluctuations accelerate these reactions, resulting in the formation of products such as aldehydes and ketones, reducing nutritional value and creating undesirable sensory properties^{37,1}.

Color changes can be observed in aquatic foods after multiple F-T cycles due to various reasons such as changes in water holding properties, protein denaturation, and changes in heme iron content. It has been determined that the L* value increases due to the increase in free water in the tissues with water dissolution²⁶. Protein denaturation and oxidation also transport water

Table 1. Studies on F-T cycles in aquatic foods

	Product name	Findings (as F-T cycles progress)	Reference
1	Catfish (<i>Silurus glanis Linne</i>) muscle	Lipid and protein oxidation increased, and the amount of heme iron decreased.	[25]
2	Common Carp (<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>) Muscle	Lipid and protein oxidation increased, water holding capacity (WHC) decreased.	[26]
3	The tilapia fillets	Weight loss, lipid oxidation and pH increased, and brightness red and yellow color values also increased.	[27]
4	Pacific white shrimp (<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i>)	Sensory and textural quality decreased significantly, total viable count, protein and lipid oxidation increased.	[28]
5	Indian Major Carps	Protein solubility, WHC, emulsifying capacity, and fillet firmness decreased.	[29]
6	Bonito (<i>Sarda sarda</i>) and bluefish (<i>Pomatomus saltator</i>)	The decrease in total iron and heme iron content was found to be greater in bluefish than in bonito.	[18]
7	Bonito (<i>Sarda sarda</i>) Fillets	Cryoprotectants, especially sodium tripolyphosphate, reduced the negative effects of F-T cycles on proteins.	[14]
8	Rainbow trout (<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>)	Sucrose, sorbitol and trehalose minimized thawing and cooking loss.	[13]
9	Asian seabass (<i>Lates calcarifer</i>)	Rainbow trout (<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>) hydrolysates reduced the formation of protein carbonyls, total sulfhydryl loss, and protein solubility. Also, the thermal properties of myofibrillar proteins are preserved	[15]
10	Minced pacific whiting	Rice Bran Hydrolysates effectively reduced protein aggregation and sulfhydryl oxidation and increased the gelling properties of proteins.	[30]
11	Marinated snakehead fish	The addition of nano fish bone has preserved the quality more than commercial cryoprotectants with its antifreeze and antioxidant properties.	[31]
12	Fish balls	Ice glazing with sodium alginate preserved WHC and textural properties. TVB-N and TVC were found to be lower, and smaller and homogeneous ice crystals were formed.	[7]
13	Mirror carp (<i>Cyprinus carpio L.</i>)	The use of ice structuring protein improved WHC and oxidation reactions and delayed the destruction of muscle structure in SEM imaging.	[16]
14	Squid (<i>Symplectoteuthis oualaniensis</i>)	Larger squid sizes (≥ 17 cm) had more reduced quality.	[32]
15	Sardine (<i>Sardinella aurita</i>)	Significant changes such as decrease in water activity and WHC, as well as color change and muscle fiber desiccation were determined.	[2]

out of the cell, causing an increase in brightness²⁷. In addition, drip loss causes decreases in ferritin, hemoglobin and myoglobin, which are water-soluble fractions of total iron, and this causes color changes¹⁸. It is also reported that color properties change depending on lipid oxidation¹⁴.

Microbiological Quality

Freezing is one of the most important methods that limits microbial activity in aquatic foods¹⁹. Freezing time, storage temperature and temperature fluctuations can cause damage to microorganism cells³⁸. However, with freezing, microorganisms lose their physical activity rather than being inhibited³⁹. Studies have shown that multiple F-T cycles, increase the total number of living organisms²⁸. In addition, the increase in TVB-N value as a result of F-T cycles may indicate increased microbial activity.¹² Changes in sensory properties such as color, taste and smell can also be considered as indicators of microbial activity. In the study conducted by Lan et al. (28), it was found that sensory properties decreased significantly during eight F-T cycles. Tissue damage and increased free water content resulting from multiple F-T

cycles can increase microbial activity. Therefore, it can be concluded that shelf life decreases as the number of F-T cycles in aquatic foods.

Reduce the Effects of Multiple Freeze-Thaw Cycles

Aquatic foods are very sensitive to F-T cycles and different studies are being carried out to reduce the negative effects^{16, 31}. Since the growth of ice crystal sizes due to temperature fluctuations in the cold chain has an important effect on the quality of aquatic foods, very rapid freezing and controlled thawing can preserve the product quality²³. In addition to controlling freezing and thawing processes, different ingredients and technological processes can also be applied. Studies have shown that different cryoprotectants prevent the negative effects that occur during the F-T cycles^{14, 13}. Similarly, the addition of hydrolysates^{15, 30}, nano fish bone³¹, ICP protein¹⁶ also help preserve many quality parameters in the products. These components reduce freeze-thaw damage by stabilizing muscle proteins, improving water-holding capacity, and inhibiting ice crystal formation and recrystallization.

Coating or glazing of products is also among the met-

hods used for protection. W. Li et al., 2024⁷ reported that fish ball glazed with sodium alginate maintained its WHC and textural properties, had lower TVB-N and TVC counts, and formed smaller and more homogeneous ice crystals. It has also been reported that ultrasound-assisted freezing can improve WHC, color, and texture, and produce smaller ice crystals, thus preventing muscle tissue damage during multiple F-T cycles³.

Conclusion

In this review, the effects of multiple F-T cycles on aquatic foods and the ways to prevent them were examined considering the literature. Multiple F-T cycles, which can be seen as a result of improper frozen cold chain applications, especially in high-protein muscle foods and therefore also in aquatic foods, are significantly deteriorating the quality of the products. The continuity of freezing and thawing processes due to temperature fluctuations leads to physical, chemical and microbiological quality changes. From an industrial standpoint, maintaining the frozen cold chain and enforcing standardized temperature control regulations are critical measures to reduce F-T cycles deterioration and to safeguard product quality and consumer trust. Therefore, carrying out the freezing and thawing processes under controlled conditions, adding different preservatives, glazing and coating, and implementing novel technological processes or using them in combination, are crucial for minimizing quality losses. New research in this topic should be planned to use existing and novel technologies and develop new protective strategies. In this way, by preserving the quality of aquatic food, more reliable and nutritious foods can be delivered to consumers. Improvements in this area are extremely important for technological development in the aquatic food industry.

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